

Run Overview Report

Project: Benjamin
Assay: Eukaryote Total RNA StdSens
Run: Run_11-8-2023_1-03-11 PM
Run Version: N/A

Acq. Analyst: DefaultUser
Acq. Time: 11/8/2023 1:03:12 PM
Signature: N/A

Virtual Gel Report

Project: Benjamin
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Egram, Gel Lane and Result Table Report

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Well# Ladder

Well# Ladder

RNA Area: 96.08
 RNA Concentration: 160.00 ng/μl

Well# Ladder				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.46	
	2	30.85	11.27	
	3	34.55	1.01	
	4	35.45	8.91	
	5	40.80	7.22	
	6	43.80	8.99	
	7	45.55	1.24	
	8	46.40	8.12	
	9	50.20	9.57	

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Well# Ladder				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
L	10	53.55	11.10	
	11	59.15	10.70	

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Well# 1 Sample 1

Well# 1 Sample 1						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.40	46.65	9.41	17.20	
2	28S	52.35	54.75	19.80	36.19	

RNA Area: 54.72
 RNA Concentration: 91.11 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.10
 RQI: 9.6 ■

Well# 1 Sample 1					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.80	1.77		
	2	45.50	9.38		
	3	53.55	23.67		

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Well# 2 Sample 2

2

Well# 2 Sample 2						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.70	46.70	4.85	12.06	
2	28S	52.45	54.85	11.27	28.01	

RNA Area: 40.23
 RNA Concentration: 66.99 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.32
 RQI: 9.6 ■

Well# 2 Sample 2					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.80	1.82		
	2	45.56	4.69		
	3	53.62	12.09		

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Well# 3 Sample 3

3

Well# 3 Sample 3

Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area
1	18S	44.40	46.60	8.31	17.85
2	28S	52.40	54.80	19.01	40.83

RNA Area: 46.55
 RNA Concentration: 77.52 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.29
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 3 Sample 3

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.50	
	2	45.46	8.13	
	3	53.56	19.99	

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Well# 4 Sample 4

4

Well# 4 Sample 4						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.45	46.75	9.38	16.93	
2	28S	52.35	55.65	19.28	34.80	

RNA Area: 55.41
 RNA Concentration: 92.27 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.06
 RQI: N/A RQI Alert: Critical Anomaly

Well# 4 Sample 4					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area		Comments
	1	23.80	1.74		
	2	45.52	9.47		
	3	53.80	23.48		
	4	56.53	4.88		

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Well# 5 Sample 5

5

Well# 5 Sample 5						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.45	46.80	13.45	16.67	
2	28S	52.45	55.75	26.84	33.25	

RNA Area: 80.72
 RNA Concentration: 134.42 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.99
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 5 Sample 5				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.59	
	2	45.57	13.79	
	3	53.85	32.63	
	4	56.62	7.02	

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Well# 6 Sample 6

6

Well# 6 Sample 6						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.45	46.80	9.94	16.36	
2	28S	52.40	55.75	19.75	32.51	

RNA Area: 60.76
 RNA Concentration: 101.18 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.99
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 6 Sample 6					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.80	1.57		
	2	45.52	10.02		
	3	53.79	23.57		

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Well# 7 Sample 7

7

Well# 7 Sample 7

Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area
1	18S	44.30	46.50	77.22	18.12
2	28S	52.25	54.60	222.48	52.20

RNA Area: 426.23

RNA Concentration: 709.76 ng/μl

Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.88

RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 7 Sample 7

Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.41	
	2	29.18	2.06	
	3	36.19	1.09	
	4	45.38	78.81	
	5	46.96	3.05	

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Well# 7 Sample 7				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	48.04	3.95	
	7	48.54	3.72	
	8	49.33	3.60	
	9	50.32	2.54	
	10	51.80	7.22	
	11	53.38	252.18	
	12	56.19	11.08	

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Well# 8 Sample 8

Well# 8 Sample 8						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.30	46.50	20.83	19.90	
2	28S	52.20	54.65	48.92	46.75	

RNA Area: 104.65
 RNA Concentration: 174.27 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.35
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 8 Sample 8					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.80	1.41		
	2	29.18	1.42		
	3	45.33	20.47		
	4	53.38	52.84		

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Well# 9 Sample 9

Well# 9 Sample 9						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.35	46.45	33.44	17.04	
2	28S	52.15	54.60	83.14	42.36	

RNA Area: 196.29
 RNA Concentration: 326.87 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.49
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 9 Sample 9				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.46	
	2	29.12	2.08	
	3	45.28	32.29	
	4	49.28	0.53	
	5	50.26	0.81	

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Well# 9 Sample 9				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	53.32	92.85	

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Well# 10 Sample 10

10

Well# 10 Sample 10						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.35	46.60	18.70	15.32	
2	28S	52.25	54.75	44.40	36.38	

RNA Area: 122.05
 RNA Concentration: 203.23 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.37
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 10 Sample 10					
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments	
	1	23.80	1.24		
	2	29.21	1.14		
	3	45.44	19.25		
	4	47.01	0.82		
	5	49.42	0.69		

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Well# 10 Sample 10				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	51.83	2.20	
	7	53.45	57.11	

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Well# 11 Sample 11

Well# 11 Sample 11						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.40	46.70	4.63	16.00	
2	28S	52.35	54.90	8.54	29.53	

RNA Area: 28.92
 RNA Concentration: 48.16 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 1.85
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 11 Sample 11				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.26	
	2	45.49	4.17	
	3	53.59	8.57	

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Well# 12 Sample 12

12

Well# 12 Sample 12						
Fragment Number	Fragment Name	Start Time	End Time	Area	% of Total Area	
1	18S	44.40	46.65	20.00	15.60	
2	28S	52.30	54.80	46.90	36.58	

RNA Area: 128.23
 RNA Concentration: 213.54 ng/μl
 Ratio[28S/18S]: 2.34
 RQI: 10.0 ■

Well# 12 Sample 12				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	1	23.80	1.15	
	2	29.19	1.16	
	3	45.45	20.85	
	4	47.01	0.88	
	5	48.68	1.18	

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Well# 12 Sample 12				
Peak State	Peak Number	Mig. Time (secs)	Corrected Area	Comments
	6	49.46	0.66	
	7	51.91	2.39	
	8	53.53	59.98	
	9	56.37	8.16	